

CARE Checklist

Topic	Item	Checklist item description	Reported on Line
Title	1	The diagnosis or intervention of primary focus followed by the words “case report”	1–2
Keywords	2	2 to 5 key words that identify diagnoses or interventions in this case report, including "case report"	46
Abstract	3a	Introduction: What is unique about this case and what does it add to the literature?	22–29
	3b	Main symptoms and/or important clinical findings	23–27, 31–34
	3c	The main diagnoses, therapeutic interventions, and outcomes	30–41
	3d	Conclusion—Take-away lesson(s) from this case	41–44
Introduction	4	One–two paragraphs summarizing why this case is unique (may include references)	49–103
Patient Information	5a	De-identified patient specific information	158–236
	5b	Primary concerns and symptoms of the patient	159–163, 190–194, 213–217
	5c	Medical, family, and psychosocial history	190 (poliomyelitis), 216–217 (headache)
	5d	Relevant past interventions with outcomes	165–168, 197–200, 220–223
Clinical Findings	6	Significant physical examination and findings	163–165, 194–196, 224–226
Timeline	7	Episode of care presented as timeline	158–236
Diagnostic Assessment	8a	Diagnostic testing (PE, labs, imaging)	117–136, 163–165, 194–196, 217–225
	8b	Diagnostic challenges	165–167, 197–200
	8c	Diagnosis (including differentials)	169–171, 196–202, 219–223
	8d	Prognosis (if applicable)	186–187, 210–211, 235–236
Therapeutic Interventions	9a	Type(s) of intervention (surgical, pharmacologic, etc.)	137–149, 175–187, 203–211, 228–236
	9b	Intervention details (dosing, procedure, duration)	171–174, 197–200, 220–223
	9c	Changes in intervention and rationale	171–174, 197–200, 221–223
Follow-up & Outcomes	10a	Clinician and patient-assessed outcomes	182–187, 208–211, 234–236
	10b	Follow-up test results	187, 210–211, 235
	10c	Intervention adherence and tolerability	172–174, 221–223

	10d	Adverse/unanticipated events	184–186
Discussion	11a	Strengths and limitations of the case	237–319
	11b	Discussion of relevant literature (with references)	237–318, 377–475
	11c	Scientific rationale for conclusions	237–318
	11d	Take-away lesson (conclusion)	314–319, 321–322
Patient Perspective	12	Patient’s own view on treatment received	324–344
Informed Consent	13	Patient gave written informed consent	106–108, 368–370